

**THE SYSTEM OF POPULATION ACCOMMODATION AND
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.
(USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE JIZZAKH REGION).**

Gapporov Azimbek Nazarovich

Senior Lecturer at the Faculty of Natural Sciences

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University. Jizzakh. Uzbekistan

Abstract: The formation of population placement systems in a certain territory depends on many factors, including the natural environment. In fact, it should be noted that the most important place in the settlement of the population is occupied by natural conditions, since the possibilities of using nature have a major impact on the development and stabilization of settlements. Therefore, the issue of the formation of the natural state and the use of natural resources in accordance with the settlement systems of the population is relevant. This article examines some regional features of nature management in Uzbekistan on the example of the Jizzakh region. The interrelation of the settlement placement system with environmental management in various agro-climatic conditions is analyzed.

Keywords: nature management, mountainous and lowland territories, water resources, human settlements, agro-climatic conditions.

Human settlements as territorial systems of population accommodation play an important role in the economic and social development of the country. The relationship between the territorial distribution of the population and the use of natural resources in territories with different natural conditions is one of the urgent problems in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The natural conditions in the republic differ geographically in accordance with the formation of natural zones and agro-climatic conditions. These factors, as the determining basis for the relationship between nature and the population of the republic, are often determined by a combination of

mountainous and lowland territories. In the regions, where there are mountainous and lowland territories, the nature of the use of natural resources and the system of housing the population differs already within one region. Especially if the flat territories were of a desert nature and were developed relatively recently, these differences are very noticeable and in some way determine the economic and social development of the territory and the way of life of the population. The territory of such villages is divided into zones where the population and household accommodation systems have been formed since ancient times and relatively recently developed and populated areas.

The Jizzakh region is one of such territories of Uzbekistan where administrative districts and population distribution systems are clearly divided into mountainous and foothill territories, as well as developed plains where there was a desert.

The nature of the territorial distribution of the population is always related to the characteristics and potential of natural conditions and resources. In recent years, the problems of using natural resources have become more acute as the population and settlements increase. Therefore, it is important to constantly monitor and evaluate the relationship of the population with nature within each region.

The territorial features of the natural conditions and resources and the system of accommodation of the population of region differ sharply in mountainous and flat territories.

The mountainous territories are located in the eastern, southern, southeastern and southwestern parts of region and represent the western parts of the Turkestan range, Chumkartau and Molguzar ranges, as well as the Nurata range, Gobduntau and Aktau mountains. The valley of the Sanzar River is formed between the Molguzar and Chumkartau ridges, and the Gallaorol intermountain depression is formed between the Nurata ridges and the Gobduntau and Aktau mountains. The climate depends on altitude, mainly continental-subtropical. The average temperature in January is $+5^{\circ}\text{C}$, in July $+28^{\circ}\text{C}$. The average annual precipitation in

the foothills ranges from 400 mm, in the highlands up to 800 mm. Precipitation falls mainly in winter and early spring periods in the form of rain and snow. The nature of the mountainous part of region is rich in rare species of vegetation and wildlife. In order to protect the flora and fauna of region, the Zomin Juniper Reserve in the Zomin Mountains and the Nurata Mountain Walnut Reserve, as well as the Zomin National Park, have been created.

The agro-climatic conditions and water resources of the mountainous territories had a very great influence in the formation of the economic structure and accommodation of the population. As correctly defined, "natural water resources and irrigation structures determine the geography of settlements in Uzbekistan"[1]. In the mountain slopes and foothills of region, where there is more precipitation, as well as natural water resources, the population has settled since ancient times, and was engaged in rain-fed, as well as irrigation agriculture on floodplains and pasture cattle breeding in the mountain slopes. Before the development of the Jizzakh steppe, population accommodation systems were formed only in the intermountain and foothill plains, in the slopes of the mountains. Some localities have a very deep historical past. Water resources were the main factors in the formation of the population accommodation system.

Table 1.

Data on administrative districts of settlements is inaccessible sparsely connected by rivers in mountainous areas.

№	Districts	The total number of the population (thousand people) and settlements. 2024		Mountainous areas	Rivers and rivulets	Number of settlements	Population size and proportion.
		population	Settlements				
1	Sh. Rashidov	243088	40	The northern slopes of the northern part of the Molguzar range	Sanzar, Ravatsai, Sayxansai and others.	19	$\frac{42045}{24.5\%}$

2	Zomin	179560	83	The northern slopes of the Molguzar range	Achchisai, Pshagarsai and others.	13	$\frac{18762}{13.5\%}$
				The northern slopes of the Molguzar range	Zominsu	16	$\frac{29285}{21.1\%}$
					Jaloirsai, Turkmansai and others.	10	$\frac{8533}{6.1\%}$
3	Yangiobod	29822	30	The northern slopes of the Molguzar range	Xojamushkentsai, Sarmichsai and others.	12	$\frac{22660}{93.7\%}$
3	Bakhmal	170575	99	The valley between the southern slopes of the Molguzar and the northern slopes of the Chumkartau ridge	Tuyatortar channel and Sanzar river within the Bakhmal district	99	$\frac{125499}{100}$
4	Gallaorol	186881	110	The southern slopes of the Nurata range.	Tangi, Savruksai, Kuramsai, Karasu	29	$\frac{25565}{18.3\%}$
				The northern slopes of Mount Gobduntau.	A lot of mountain rivulets	18	$\frac{22923}{16.4\%}$
				The northern part of the Molguzar range	Sanzar river within the Gallaorol district.	16	$\frac{20831}{14.9\%}$
5	Forish	98405	112	The southern slopes of the Nurata range.	Kuramsai and others.	25	$\frac{21455}{27.8\%}$
				The northern slopes of the Nurata range.	Uxumsai, Majrumsai, Uchmasai and more than 20 mountain rivulets.	46	$\frac{36242}{47\%}$

Source: Region Static Control data, region map.

As indicated in the table, a large proportion of the population lives in a mountainous area directly dependent on rivers. The remaining settlements of these mountains are located in the foothill plains and their farms are connected by artificial irrigation systems. As can be seen, the historical development of the national economy of region is closely connected by small mountain rivers. A special place is occupied by the Sanzar River, which, 123 km from Chumkartau to Lake Tuzkan, plays an important role in the development of over 150 settlements, including the city of Jizzakh, which is located on the cone of the outflow of this river. The length of the remaining rivers is no more than 40 km, but they also have a great influence in economic activity and territorial distribution of the population. Artificial reservoirs also play an important role in the life of the population. In order to irrigate the foothill areas and provide for the population, several reservoirs have been built. Of these, the largest are Jizzakh reservoir, with an area of 13,8 km. sq. and a volume of 100 million cubic meters. on the Sanzar River basin and Zomin reservoir with an area of 9.3 km. sq. and a volume of 52 million cubic meters. on the Zominsuv River.

The economic activity of the population of the mountain districts is determined by several areas of agriculture. In horticulture, the cultivation of apple trees, grapes and nuts prevails, in rain-fed agriculture wheat, in pasture cattle breeding sheep farming. The nature of the population's activities varies according to altitude zones. Along the rivers, the population is engaged in gardening, along the slopes of the mountains, rain-fed agriculture and pasture livestock farming.

The plain part of region is located in the north and northwest and consists of the Jizzakh steppe and the Pre-Kyzylkum plain. The Jizzakh steppe, as it is known, was developed in the second half of the twentieth century. Before the development of the plains, they were used as temporary pastures for nomadic livestock breeders. The climate of the plains is dry, hot and continental. The average temperature in January is 1⁰C, in July +30⁰C, maximum +45⁰C. The average annual precipitation is 250 mm. Precipitation falls mainly in winter and early spring in the form of rain. Vegetation

consists of ephemera and halophytes. In the north of the plain part of region, the Aydarkol lake system was formed. This system consists of three lakes; Tuzkan, Arnasai and Aydarkol, and is of great importance in the natural complex of the territory, as well as in the economic potential of region. There is an Arnasai Aquatic Bird Sanctuary in Lake Arnasai. In the territory of the Farish district, work is underway to organize the Farish-Nurata Biosphere Reserve.

An artificial irrigation system was created in the developed territory of the Mirzachol and Jizzakh steppe in order to develop cotton farming and the flat part of region turned from a desert into a developed agricultural region for a relatively short time. The fields are irrigated through canals by the waters of the Syr Darya River. Urban-type settlements and roads were built, and people were settled from the mountain areas and from the regions of the Ferghana Valley. Thus, new cotton-growing administrative districts were formed - Arnasai, Mirzachul, Pakhtakor, Dustlik, Zafarabad, Zarbdar, which currently produce the bulk of agricultural products. During the years of independence, new directions of crop production based on farms developed in these districts, except cotton, wheat, melons, and vegetables are grown. Instead of the state-owned economic system, the private sector was formed.

Industry in the region plays a crucial role in the processing of agricultural raw materials. Light industry enterprises for processing raw cotton into fiber and food industry enterprises operate mainly in the cities.

Thus, the territory of region can be divided into two parts according to the use of natural resources: mountainous, where the population farms extensively, occupying more and more territory, and this causes damage to the natural environment and protected areas. In subsequent years, the population of mountain districts is constantly growing and therefore the influence of human economic activity on nature increases in these territories. The mountain districts of region have large territories, the majority of the population lives in them, and the needs of this

population are constantly growing[3]. Therefore, some problems related to the use of natural resources arise and worsen. These problems worsen as the population increases, in the following order:

1. The number of settlements and population density are growing;
2. The area of pasture and rain-fed lands regarding settlement is constantly decreasing;
3. Due to the increased use of natural water resources, there is a growing shortage of water both for drinking and for irrigation of gardens and vegetable plantations.
4. The population is increasingly approaching protected areas, destroying rare species of plants and animals.
5. The problems of providing for the population are becoming more acute as settlements are formed without a specific plan.

In the mountain districts, the population is growing not only as a result of natural growth. In the independent years of the republic, there was a growing tendency for the population to return to their ancestral places where their ancestors lived. So, in a short time, settlements multiplied in the mountainous territories.

In the developed territories, settlements during the USSR were provided with all necessary resources and equipment, since these lands were the main bases of cotton growing. After the independence of the republic, farmers appeared instead of state farms and the requirements for labor and labor resources changed. The most important feature of the economic activity and life of the population in these districts is that it is completely dependent on the water regime of the Syrdarya River, and therefore the problems of transit rivers in Central Asia directly concern the population and economy of these districts. Therefore, the rational use of water resources is the main problem of the plain territory of region.

In recent years, differences between mountainous and lowland territories have been growing in economic development, as well as in the location and living

standards of the population, which significantly affects the economic and social development of region. The solution to this problem can be the organization and management of a harmonious, interconnected economic development between the mountainous and lowland parts of region. This relationship is primarily related to the natural potentials of the territory and the proper organization of the use of labor resources[4]. Because the plain districts have great potential in creating industrial enterprises and housing the population, and the mountains have huge recreational resources. Thus, two zones can be created in the territory of region: an industrial, urbanized, high-density lowland districts zone and an environmentally friendly, recreational and tourist zone of mountain districts.

As can be seen, the economic development and living standards of the region population depend on various natural conditions. If we organize the rational use of natural conditions and resources of the area and the appropriate management of economic activities, these differences can only positively affect the economic development of the territory and the standard of living of the population.

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